

THE EFFECT OF P2R (PREVIEW READ, REVIEW) ISTRATEGY ON STUDENTS' READING COMPREIENSION AT GRADE VIII MTs NEGERI 2 PADANGSIDIMPUAN

Ermina Seriwayat Nainggolan¹, Yulina Oktaviani Harahap², Yulinda Oktaviana Harahap³

¹ STKIP Padang Lawas, Indonesia. E-mail: nainggolanermina30@gmail.com

² STIKES Paluta Husada, Indonesia. E-mail: yuliaoktavianiharahap@gmail.com

³ Universitas Prof Doktor Hafiz MPH, Indonesia. E-mail: yulindaoktaviana@gmail.com

INFORMASI ARTIKEL

Submitted : 2026-05-31
Review : 2026-05-31
Accepted : 2026-05-31
Published : 2026-05-31

KEYWORDS

Preview, Read, Review (P2r) Strategy, Reading Comprehension, Strategi P2r (Preview, Read, Review), Pemahaman Membaca.

A B S T R A C T

This research discussed about the effect of P2R (Preview, Read, Review) strategy on Students' Reading Comprehension at Grade VIII MTs N 2 Padangsidimpuan. The problems of this research were the students still got low grade with average 68; meanwhile the standard of English competency in this school was 80, students did not know the strategies, stress and tired in reading comprehension and students were lack of vocabulary and motivation in reading. The aims of this research were to describe and to examine the effect of P2R (Preview, Read, Review) strategy on Students' Reading Comprehension at Grade VIII MTs N 2 Padangsidimpuan. This research employed experimental research. The population of this research was the eight grade of MTs Negeri 2 Padangsidimpuan. The total of population were 4 classes. Then, the sample of the research was 2 classes, experiment class (VIII-1) and control class (VIII-2). It was taken randomly after conducting normality and homogeneity test. To collect the data, researcher used test for measuring students' Reading Comprehension achievement. To analysis the data, the researcher used t-test. Based on the result of the research, researcher showed the description of the data was found that the result of experimental class was higher than control class (81.35>77.65), and the score of tcount was bigger than ttable (4.11> 1.67). It means that the hypothesis alternative (Ha) was accepted. It was concluded that there was the significant effect of P2R (Preview, Read, Review) strategy on Students' Reading Comprehension at Grade VIII MTs N 2 Padangsidimpuan.

Penelitian ini membahas tentang pengaruh strategi P2R (Preview, Read, Review) terhadap Pemahaman Membaca Siswa Kelas VIII MTs Negeri 2 Padangsidimpuan. Permasalahan penelitian ini adalah siswa masih mendapatkan nilai rendah dengan rata-rata 68; sementara standar kompetensi Bahasa Inggris di sekolah ini Adalah 80, siswa tidak mengetahui strategi, mengalami stres dan kelelahan dalam pemahaman membaca dan siswa kurang kosakata dan motivasi dalam membaca. Tujuan penelitian ini adalah untuk mendeskripsikan dan menguji pengaruh strategi P2R (Preview, Read, Review) terhadap Pemahaman Membaca Siswa Kelas VIII MTs Negeri 2 Padangsidimpuan. Penelitian ini menggunakan metode penelitian eksperimental.

Populasi penelitian ini adalah siswa kelas delapan MTs Negeri 2 Padangsidimpuan. Jumlah populasi Adalah 4 kelas. Kemudian, sampel penelitian adalah 2 kelas, kelas eksperimen (VIII-1) dan kelas kontrol (VIII-2). Sampel diambil secara acak setelah dilakukan uji normalitas dan homogenitas. Untuk mengumpulkan data, peneliti menggunakan tes untuk mengukur pencapaian Pemahaman Membaca siswa. Untuk menganalisis data, peneliti menggunakan uji-t. Berdasarkan hasil penelitian, peneliti menunjukkan deskripsi data yang menunjukkan bahwa hasil kelas eksperimen lebih tinggi daripada kelas kontrol (81,35 > 77,65), dan skor t hitung lebih besar daripada t tabel (4,11 > 1,67). Artinya, hipotesis alternatif (Ha) diterima. Disimpulkan bahwa terdapat pengaruh signifikan strategi P2R (Preview, Read, Review) terhadap Pemahaman Membaca siswa di Kelas VIII MTs N 2 Padangsidimpuan.

BACKGROUND

English is very important and has many interrelationships with various aspects of life owned by human being. In English, there are four skills that must be mastered. They are listening, speaking, reading and writing. These are very important to be learned and mastered. In this case, the researcher focuses on reading that is one of problematics in English learning, especially in reading comprehension. Reading is a complex process that includes physical and mental process. The physic activities occur by stimulation of the eyes. These activities are begun by observing pictures or sounds of the written language. Reading is one of the important skills. By reading, students get much information and increase knowledge and experience. By having a good skill in reading, the students will be easy to get information from many sources from books, magazines, newspapers, brochures and etcetera. On the other hand, if the students have a good ability in reading, they will be successful in their studying because they understand what the text talk about.

Reading is an activity to transfer the knowledge from the text to mind. The knowledge is very important. It is impossible to gain information from the text without reading. Therefore, there are few reasons why reading necessary in the life. First, Reading is an essential skill for learners. For most of these learners, it is the most important skill to be mastered in order to ensure success not only in learning English. But also, in learning any contents classes where reading in English is required. Second, reading activates mind, gets a lot of knowledge about many things in the world such as sciences, technologies, sports, arts, cultures, religious, etcetera. Besides, reading makes the brain relax, interacts with the feelings and thought, obtains information and improving the science or knowledge and also gives pleasure.

First, based on interview with the teacher, most of the students still get low grade with 68 grade meanwhile the standard of English competency in this school is 80. So, the researcher wants to solve this problem by examining a reading strategy that is chosen. Second, most of the students do not understand the text that they read and do not know the strategies, stress and tired in reading comprehension. They do not have tricks to make them easier, read without pencil in hand, highlighting, jotting notes, and marking key vocabularies. So, they do not know how to improve their comprehension in reading, such as; reading assignment with same ways, unable to analyze the purpose,

unable to adjust their speed to suit their purpose and unable to make questions in their mind. Next, the students are lack of vocabulary and motivation in reading, seldom to practice, and lack of attention about the important of reading. They just read a text, and they accept what is in print directly without compare and connect what they are reading with what they have known. So, before reading, they do not find out what the assignment about, and check the length of an assignment before reading and read until the assignment is completed only.

Continuously, they also can not make the inference of the text and do not know what the text talk about. So, they comprehend the text well. Then, reading becomes the burden of their life. Besides, many students accept everything they read at face value, they seldom sit back and examine the authors' ideas, sources, evidences, or choice of words with critical eyes.

To solve the problems in reading, there are some alternatives of reading strategies that are available and applicable. As researcher know, there are many techniques and many strategies that can solve students' problem in reading comprehension, and also could increase the students' ability in reading comprehension, such as skimming, scanning, and P2R (Preview Read Review). Skimming is a strategy that can help the students to read faster. In addition, skimming is a reading strategy to take the point of something in reading. Meanwhile scanning is a reading strategy to read the detail information faster. In another word, scanning is the ability to find or to locate specific information. These strategies are useful in speed reading or reading faster. So, by using both of them, the students can read fast, but lack of comprehension of all the text. It means that not all the content of the text can comprehend well because these strategies emphasize in an important thing.

From the problems that mention above, the researcher chose P2R reading strategies. It is caused that the suitable theories in this research that researcher found in the field are behaviour and cognitive theory. Behaviour theory assumptions that children attitude is the result of the experience with environment stimulus. Then, learning in association between ancient that can be observed, they are stimulus and response. (Omrod, 2008).

Thus, this theory also said as stimulus and response theory. It is caused that by giving stimulus students can give response. Next, cognitive theory assumption (Smaldino, 2012) that cognitive process creates a mental process to get the information from short-term memory to the long-term memory; new information will be saved in short-term memory, then repeating information and finally the information will be saved in long-term memory. Based on cognitive theory, learning can happen from students' thinking and should be active in processing the information.

Then, based on cognitive theory learning strategy (Sukardo, 2010) gives good effect in arranging the information; the students can use their knowledge based on their scheme. One of applications of cognitive theory in learning strategy is: advance organizer, reading heading, and outlines to guide the students in processing information. It is introduced by David Ausubel. Cognitive theory has philosophy; it is the way in which we learn. It means that knowledge of someone is based on thought.

So, based on the explanation of behaviour and cognitive theory can effect P2R (Preview, Read, and Review) strategy to achieve reading comprehension. It is caused P2R strategy is a strategy in teaching learning process. Thus, the stimulus that gives to the students as a behaviour theory and response includes in behaviour and cognitive theory. Further, the cognitive theory impresses the mind process in memory.

Based on the explanations above, the researcher feels interested to do the research about this problem and choses P2R (Preview, Read and Review) strategy, and it gives some reasons about this strategy. First, students' learning materials are text books which contain a lot of passages. The passage consists of some paragraphs that contains and builds some ideas and information. Naturally, a text consists of one topic that contains much important information that readers must know. Conceptually, P2R is designed to identify all of important information from the text that readers read. Further, P2R is a strategy to comprehend the text. It has three steps, Preview, it means to activate background knowledge and relate it to the text. Read the text actively. Review, it means that read all the contents of the text to answer the question or make the deep comprehension. So, read many times is better than read once, it is very important to us, mainly read the text of English, especially for beginner level, because P2R strategy is Designed for the easy to average materials. So, the students must read two times or three times so that they comprehend the passage or text.

Next, by the three steps, preview, read and review, the readers must read all the text carefully without passing one word to another word. It means that the reader must analyze word by word. Finally, many researchers have done research about P2R strategy, and this P2R strategy has been proven as an efficient strategy in reading comprehension. Moreover, the theory that will be used in this research is P2R strategy. This theory has been created by Diana L. Van Blerkom.¹⁰ It provides a mechanism for increasing understanding and memory in Reading Comprehension. Based on the metacognitive theory, this learning strategy refers to the behaviour and mind process that is used by the students which influence to their learning, include memory and metacognitive process. This is the theory that would be examined by the researcher for hypothesis in this research. Based on the illustration above, the researcher is interested in conducting experimental research with the purpose to solve student's problem in reading comprehension by the title "The Effect of P2R (Preview, Read, Review) Strategy on Students' Reading Comprehension at Grade VIII MTs Negeri 2 Padangsidimpuan.

Method

This research is conducted with quantitative research with experimental method. Airisian (1992) said, "Experimental research is the only type of research that can test hypothesis to establish cause and effect." And then, Creswell says, "Experimental research included the experiment with the random assignment of subject to treatment condition as well as quasi experiment that use none randomized. (Cresswell, 2000)

From the definition above, researcher concluded that the experiment is a kind of research that has aim to know the causal effect relationship between one or more variable to other variables. In this research, the researcher uses two classes, as an experiment class and as a control class. The experiment class is the class that taught with P2R strategy, as a treatment. Meanwhile the control class is the class that taught with using conventional strategy or without treatment. So, the population in this research is the whole of the students at grade VIII MTs Negeri 2 Padangsidimpuan consisted of 4 classes with 148 students. In taking the sampling, the researcher uses random sampling. The researcher choses two classes. The tricks to use random sampling are using a lottery, ordinal, random number table or computer. But, before using random sampling, the writer uses normality and homogeneity test. The researcher collected by giving the multiple-choice test. Cryil says, "A multiple-choice questions

(MCQs) is the test item usually set out in such a way that the candidate is required to select the answer from a number of given options, only one of which is correct.”⁷ In this research, the test consisted of 40 questions, where 20 for pre-test, and 20 for post-test by choosing an answer from the 4 options to prepare the students’ reading comprehension. This test is given to both class, experiment and control class. To find out the scores of the students’ answer, the researcher gave 5 score for each item. Thus, the maximum score of test is 100. In collecting data to determine the result of the research, the researcher uses test to students. In this research, the researcher uses the technique of data analysis using normality, homogeneity and hypothesis test.

Result and Discussion

Based on the theory and related findings, the researcher discussed the result of this research and compared with the related findings. First, the result of a research by using skimming strategy was found that mean score was 76.84 and the hypothesis was accepted. It means, there was the effect of skimming strategy on students’ achievement in reading comprehension. Second, the mean score result of a research by using Prediction Information from the Picture was 73.93.

The hypothesis concluded that this strategy was better than conventional strategy. Then, the research by using P2R (Preview, Read, Review) strategy to find mind ideas showed that the result of the mean score of the second cycle was 77.5. It means, the implication of this strategy can increase the students reading comprehension to find the mind ideas. It can be seen based on score result in the first cycle 63.86 and the second cycle 77.5. Further, the researcher found that using P2R (Preview, Read, Review) strategy showed the result of mean score in experimental class was 81.35 and control class was 77.65. It means the result and hypothesis testing showed that P2R (Preview, Read, Review) strategy has the effect, and hypothesis alternative (H_a) is accepted and hypothesis zero (H_0) is rejected. It can be seen from last score of the calculation above, It was indicated that the score of experimental class was bigger than control class ($81.35 > 77.65$), and also indicated to $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($4.11 > 1.67$).

Based on the analysis above, the researcher concluded that using P2R (Preview, Read, Review) strategy is better than using skimming strategy with the result $81.35 > 76.84$. Then, P2R (Preview, Read, Review) strategy is better than using Prediction information from the picture with mean score $81.35 > 73.93$. Thus, the researcher concluded that P2R (Preview, Read, Review) strategy also was an effective and efficient strategy and can improve the students’ reading comprehension.

Conclusion

Based on the result of data analysis that had described in the previous chapter, the researcher concluded that there is the significant effect of P2R (Preview, Read, Review) strategy on Students’ Reading Comprehension of Recount Text at MTs Negeri 2 Padangsidempuan. So, the hypothesis alternative (H_a) is accepted. It is based on the mean score of experimental class after using P2R (Preview, Read, Review) strategy is bigger than control class ($81.35 > 77.65$) and proven with t_{count} is higher than t_{table} ($4.11 > 1.67$). The hypothesis zero (H_0) was rejected. Thus, the researcher concluded that P2R (Preview, Read, Review) strategy is an effective and efficient on students’ reading comprehension.

REFERENCES

- _____. 2000. Teaching by Principles an Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy the Second Edition. California: Longman.
- _____. 2004. Language Assessment Principles and Classroom Practice. USA: Longman.
- _____. 2008. Taking Charge of Your Learning A Guide to College Succes. Boston: Wadsworth/Thomson.
- Blerkom, Diana L Van. 2000. College Study Skill Becoming a Strategic Learner. Belmont, CA: Thomson Wadsworth.
- Brown, H. Douglas. 2003. Language Assessment Practical and language Practice. San Francisco: Longman.
- Creswell, Jhon. 2000. Research Design Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approaches Second Edition. USA: Prentice Hall.
- Gay, L. R and Peter Airaisan. 1992. Educational Research for Analysis and Application. America: Prentice Hall.
- Haryadi. 2008. Retorika Membaca Model, Metode, dan Teknik. Semarang: Rumah Indonesia.
- Irianto, Agus. 2003. Statistik Konsep Dasar dan Aplikasinya. Padang: P2PLTK,
- Nurhadi. 2005. Membaca Cepat dan Efektif. Bandung: Sinar Baru Algresindo.
- Ormrod, Jeanne Ellis. 2008. Psikologi Pendidikan. Translated by Wahyu Indianti from "Psychology of Education". Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Rahim, Farida. 2008. Pengajaran Membaca di Sekolah Dasar: Edisi kedua. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara
- Soedarso. 2006. Speed Reading: Sistem Membaca Cepat dan Efektif. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Sudijono, Anas. 2005. Pengantar Statistik Pendidikan. Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Tarigan, Henry Guntur. 2009. Membaca sebagai Suatu Keterampilan Berbahasa. Jakarta: Bandung Angkasa.